

MODERN TENDENCIES OF LEXICOGRAPHY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13336143>

Modern trends in English lexicography are associated with the emergence and rapid development of such branches of linguistics as corpus linguistics and computational linguistics. Corpus linguistics deals with the compilation of various electronic corpora for research in various linguistic fields. Computational linguistics is a branch of linguistics in which computer science methods are used to analyze and synthesize language and speech. Computer lexicography deals with the design, compilation, use and evaluation of electronic dictionaries. Electronic dictionaries are fundamentally different in form, content and functions from conventional dictionaries. Among the most significant differences: 1) the use of multimedia tools; 2) navigation help pointers in Windows-oriented software; 3) the use of sound, animation, audio and visual (pictures, videos) elements, as well as interactive exercises and games; 4) a variety of search and access methods that allow the user to determine the output in several ways; 5) access to information and its search are no longer determined by the internal, traditionally alphabetical organization of the dictionary, but by the nonlinear structure of the text; 6) the use of hyperlinks that allow you to easily and quickly cross-reference words within the article or other words related to this entry.

For the first time this point on lexicography was expressed with certainty by the prominent Soviet linguist Academician L.V. Shcherba. In the preface to the Russian-French dictionary (1936), he wrote: «I consider it extremely wrong that our qualified linguists disdain for dictionary work. How did she get such a ridiculous name «compilation» of dictionaries. And indeed, our linguists, and even more so our «compilers» of vocabulary, insisted that the work should be of a scientific nature and in no way consist in a mechanical comparison of some ready-made elements».

The last decade was marked by a significant rise in lexicographic activity and the release of a large number of Russian-language author's words of new types, the subject of the lexicographical description of which is paraliterature and its derivatives, namely comics, feature films and computer games, computer games, fantasy.

Lexicographers came to the creation of qualitatively new reference books from the point of view of the addressee, the issue of choosing sources.

It should be especially noted that the prototype of the new author's words are the projects of the projects of reference books created by readers for the works of the fantasy genre, which are of great interest among users. First of all, this circumstance is associated with the lack of professional reference books for modern works of the fantasy genre, which is difficult to understand without certain cultural, historical and mythological knowledge.

Modern trends in English lexicography:

The modern period in the development of the lexicography of the English language can be called "scientific or historical", since it is based on the following concepts:

- 1) compilation of dictionaries according to the historical principle;
- 2) replacing the prescriptive or normative principle of compiling dictionaries with a systemic descriptive approach;
- 3) description of vocabulary as a system.

The first scientific dictionary was Roger's Thesaurus, but the pearl of English lexicography that best embodied these concepts is the Oxford English Dictionary, the largest lexicographic project of the 19th and 20th centuries. Work on it began under the auspices of the Royal Philological Society in 1857, with the first volume published in 1888 and the last in 1933. The dictionary is edited by Sir James Murray. Roger's thesaurus belongs to a special group of dictionaries - ideographic. In thesaurus dictionaries, vocabulary is organized according to a thematic principle. Roger began his work by dividing the conceptual field of the English language into four large classes: abstract relations, space, matter and spirit (mind, will, feelings). These classes are further subdivided into several genera, which, in turn, are subdivided into a certain number of species. Each species includes numbered groups. These groups (there are 1000 of them in total) are designated by words with a sufficiently broad semantics, which makes it possible to combine under them a number of words that are close in meaning.

However, soon after the publication of the dictionary, it became clear that it is very difficult to use it. Practice required a reasonable synthesis of the ideographic and alphabetical arrangement of words. So Roger added an alphabetical index to the dictionary, giving each word information about its place in ideographic classification. Roger's thesaurus should be recognized as an outstanding phenomenon in world lexicography. Its main advantage is that it

was the first scientifically substantiated attempt to create a kind of mock-up of a logically ordered language dictionary.

Recently, in the lexicography of the English language, there has been a clear tendency to reflect linguistic phenomena in direct connection with the elements of culture, thereby describing the influence of culture on the formation of language. An example is Longman Dictionary of English and Culture, Macmillan Dictionary.

The list of used literature:

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4. Halliday, M. A. K. (2007). Lexicology: a short introduction. Colin Yallop. London: Continuum. pp. 56–57. ISBN 978-1-4411-5054-7. OCLC 741690096.
5. Joseph, Brian D.; Janda, Richard D., eds. (2003), "The Handbook of Historical Linguistics", *The Handbook of Historical Linguistics*, Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd, p. 183, ISBN 9780631195719.

